

Working to Leave or Living to Work? A Study on DCLC Employees' Quality Work Life Factors and its Impact on Turnover Intention

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Abstract:- Turnover intentions are the main concern for an organization as this corresponds to the actual behavior. This, however, could be solved if the quality of work life of employees is satisfied. To address this, the purpose of this study is to determine through a quantitative research design whether the quality of work life factors (development, participation, compensation, supervision, and working environment) has a negative impact on turnover intentions of employees at Dr. Carlos S. Lanting College. Purposive sampling was utilized among the 152 teaching and non-teaching employees and accomplished the questionnaire, which includes the Quality of Work Life Factors Scale and Turnover Intention Scale (TIS-6). The data were statistically analyzed using multiple regression analysis. Findings indicated that quality of work life significantly predicts turnover intentions; however, it has been found that among the five factors, only three were significant with turnover intentions. In addition, only compensation and work environment negatively predicted turnover intentions, while in contrast, development positively predicted turnover intentions of employees. In conclusion, this demonstrates that when employees perceive they have insufficient compensation and are employed in an unsafe and unpleasant work environment, therefore it would lead them to have higher turnover intentions. Finally, it is recommended that the institution concentrates on developing and implementing compensation and work environment policies and programs in order to reduce the employee turnover rate.

Keywords:- Turnover Intentions, Quality of Work Life, Development, Compensation, Work Environment.

I. INTRODUCTION

Working to leave or living to work? Do employees only acquire jobs so that they can leave eventually, or so that they can make it a significant part of their lives? Employees are the most valuable asset of an organization; hence their loss would have a detrimental effect on the organization's performance and profitability. It is therefore critical for any organization to devote considerable attention to them. Employees must be contented with their occupations in order to stay with the organization for an extended period of time. However, some employees intend to leave the organization in search of a more favorable opportunity. As a result, the immediate threat of employee

turnover to a company is the employee replacement costs associated with recruiting, hiring, and training new employees. Similarly, the negative consequences would be the disruption of the organization's function, resulting in decreasing performance and unfulfilled daily functions (Schlechter et al., 2016).

Indeed, turnover is a significant problem for organizations due to today's intense global competition, particularly in the area of human resource management. Therefore, an employee's turnover intention could be utilized as a strategy to prevent turnover since this frequently predicts the employee's actual quitting behavior within the organization (Windon et al., 2019).

Consequently, even educational institutions such as Dr. Carlos S. Lanting College, which has been in service to a diverse population of learners for over 37 years, have experienced inevitable turnover of their teaching and non-teaching employees. In order to withstand these intentions, the company should establish a suitable quality of work life that meets the physiological, psychological, social, and economic needs of their employees (Akar, 2018). In which there are five factors that influence the quality of work life, namely development, participation, compensation, supervision, and work environment (Adikoeswanto et al., 2020).

In this regard, the research aims to concentrate on the factors affecting the quality of work life and their effect on the turnover intentions of the teaching and non-teaching employees of Dr. Carlos S. Lanting College.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Employees are essential to an organization's success, and as such, they should be valued, as there are several costs associated with the loss of an employee, whether direct or indirect. The various expenditures may include those associated with recruiting, selection, and training. Thus, in order to maximize the return on investment made in employees, it is critical to focus on lowering employee turnover rates, as this acts to demotivate the current employees and also results in a loss for the company (Jha, 2009). However, the duration of an employee's tenure at an organization is unpredictable due to a variety of factors. Individuals will alter or leave their jobs and organizations to the extent that it is convenient for them. The intention to leave a job or organization is a necessary condition for

leaving, which is frequently referred to as turnover intention (Belete, 2018).

Turnover intention can be defined as an employee's desire to leave the organization. These intentions are statement that concerns specific conduct of behavior (Mosadeghrad, 2013). In addition, the turnover intention is the likelihood that an individual plans to leave or change jobs voluntarily within a specified time period which results in a real turnover. With this, it is identified that the intention to leave is the best predictor of their actual departure (Winda et al., 2019). Therefore, turnover intention can be used to determine the likelihood of personnel leaving the organization, and this enables the identification of opportunities to reduce overall turnover.

Indeed that most of the time, an employee's life is spent on their jobs, so it is important that organizations must take strategic measures to reduce the turnover intentions. Therefore, a more attractive environment and a better quality of work life are critical to attracting and retaining qualified professionals in order to maintain a competitive edge over other organizations. Quality of work life refers to an employee's contentment with their working life. It emphasizes the quality of the relationship between the employees and the working environment (Raduan et al., 2006).

Quality of work life is a multidimensional notion that encompasses a variety of factors that have an effect on how people perform their jobs and are also evaluated when determining the quality of work life. It motivates people to perform effectively, and enhancing employees' quality of life is a necessary condition for increasing their productivity (Adhikari and Gautam, 2010). Therefore, the management is expected to have a thorough understanding of the concept of quality of work life and how it relates to employee well-being. For the organization, quality of work life will be one of the aspects that contribute to efforts to develop high productivity and reduce employees' desire to leave the company (Afsar et al., 2014).

In addition, Walton (1975) pioneered the concept of quality of work life and initially proposed categorizing it into eight distinct dimensions. Nonetheless, other research redefined the aspects of quality of work life in a variety of ways. In this research, the five factors of the quality of work life adapted from the study of Adikoeswanto et al. (2020) to be analyzed are the development, participation, compensation, supervision, and work environment. Given that the study was done in Asia, it is strongly believed that the same factors would apply in the context of the Philippines because it holds a similar working culture.

The operational definition of the five factors of the quality of work life are as follows:

Development refers to formal training and education, work experience, relationships, and personality assessments, as well as skills and abilities that assist employees in preparing for future jobs and positions that can be used for long-term personal and professional growth (Jehanzeb and Mohanty, 2018).

Participation is a process through which employees take control of their work and engage in conditions that include their engagement in work-related decisions (Khalid and Nawab, 2018). Employees share their task-related decision-making authority with their superiors through this approach.

Compensation can be described as the type of income and financial benefits obtained by employees as a result of their employment connection, and it is classified as direct such as salaries, overtime pay, and bonuses and indirect compensation such as insurance plans, educational help, reimbursements, and other benefits (Ogunnaike et al., 2016).

Supervision is the total amount of helpful social interactions accessible in a supervised workplace. It is the manifestation of goodwill and positive feelings, as well as the relationship of trust and empathy demonstrated by superiors in a positive social environment (Orgambidez and Almeida, 2020).

Work Environment refers to the organizational culture in which employees perform their duties. It is associated with the organizational climate in which employees accomplish their jobs in a conducive and safe work environment that can attract people since their demands are addressed (Hanaysha, 2016).

With this, the person-organization fit theory by Jennifer Chatman (1989) will be applied, as it addresses the similarity and congruence of an individual and the organization as a whole. This includes the notion that creating value congruence between the individual and the organization is a determining factor in making an employment decision. In other words, if an employee is integrated into an organization according to their needs, the employee is more likely to stay (Olubiyi et al., 2019). To support this, Hoffman and Woehr (2006) discovered a consistent relationship between person-organization fit and turnover, indicating that it is a significant predictor of turnover intentions, allowing for a better understanding of the impact of quality of work life factors on employee turnover.

The researchers, based on the above literature and figure 1, hypothesized that there is an inverse impact of quality of work life factors (development, participation, compensation, supervision, and work environment) on turnover intentions of employees at Dr. Carlos S. Lanting College.

Fig. 1: Conceptual framework on the inverse impact of quality of work life factors on turnover intentions

Note. X = Independent Variable; Y = Dependent Variable

A. Statement of the Problem

The research aims to determine whether the quality of work life factors would negatively lead to turnover intentions of employees at Dr. Carlos S. Lanting College. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

- What is the demographics profile of the employees according to their: a) sex, b) age, c) educational background, d) tenure of employment, and e) nature and category of employment?
- What is the relationship between quality of work life factors (development, participation, compensation, supervision, and work environment) and turnover intentions?
- What is the impact of the quality of work life factors (development, participation, compensation, supervision, and work environment) on turnover intentions?

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Participants

The research used a quantitative design to gather data and identified respondents through purposive sampling technique due to specific qualifications that they should be either teaching or non-teaching employees of Dr. Carlos S. Lanting College. The research involved 152 participants, with 101 teaching employees (66.4%) and 51 non-teaching employees (33.6%) from Dr. Carlos S. Lanting College. In addition, there were 63 males (41.4%) and 89 females (58.6%), which indicates a higher number of respondents of females; however, this slight sex difference among the

respondents has little to no effect on the results. While in table 1, the other demographic profile of the participants, such as their age, highest educational attainment, employment tenure, and their nature of employment, whether contractual, probationary, or regular, were presented. Furthermore, participants whose highest educational attainments fell under high school graduates were guided by the researchers in answering the questionnaire to better understand the items for precise responses.

B. Ethical Research

Prior to conducting the study, the researchers forwarded a permit to study letter (see Appendix A) to the Senior Vice President and President/CEO of Dr. Carlos S. Lanting College in order to inform and request their permission for the researchers to disseminate survey questionnaires to the target participants which are the employees of the institution. Before proceeding with the distribution of the questionnaire, the researchers created an informed consent form (see Appendix C) that aims to acquire the target participants' consent to participate in the study. The form included information regarding the study's purpose and background, the procedure and time the participants shall consume upon answering the two questionnaires, risks, confidentiality, and the benefits of participating. It also disclosed that participation in the study is voluntary, and respondents may withdraw anytime with and without an explanation, whereas the responses gathered would be utilized solely for research purposes.

		<i>F</i>	%
Sex	Male	63	41.4
	Female	89	58.6
Age	20-30 years old	53	34.9
	31-40 years old	37	24.3
	41-50 years old	33	21.7
	>50 years old	29	19.1
	High School Graduate	23	15.1
Educational Attainment	Bachelor's Degree	71	46.7
	MA/MS Degree	44	28.9
	Doctorate Degree	14	9.2
Employment Tenure	<1 year	15	9.9
	1-5 years	52	34.2
	6-10 years	20	13.2
	11-15 years	35	23.0
	16-20 years	16	10.5
	21-25 years	4	2.6
	26-30 years	8	5.3
	>30 years	2	1.3
Employment Category	Teaching Employees	101	66.4
	Non-Teaching Employees	51	33.6
Employment Nature	Contractual	47	30.9
	Probationary	14	9.2
	Regular	91	59.9
	Total	152	100.0

Table 1: Profile of the Respondents

C. Research Instrument

The instruments used were the Quality of Work Life Factors Scale developed by Dodot Adikoeswanto et al. (2020) and the Turnover Intention Scale (TIS-6) developed by Gert Roodt (2004) to respectively measure the employees' quality of work life and turnover intentions. In addition, the researchers emailed the instrument's authors to obtain permission to utilize their scales in the current study (see Appendix B).

Quality of Work Life Factors Scale (see Appendix D). This was used to measure the quality of the work life of employees. It is composed of 15 items and rated with a 5-point Likert scale ranging from strongly disagree to strongly agree. The scale has 5 factors which are development ($\alpha = 0.72$), participation ($\alpha = 0.88$), compensation ($\alpha = 0.90$), supervision ($\alpha = 0.82$), and work environment ($\alpha = 0.61$) and the reported Cronbach alpha coefficients has a good and acceptable internal consistency and reliability. Lastly, the scores obtained were calculated by averaging each of the factor items.

Turnover Intention Scale (TIS-6) (see Appendix E). This was used to measure the turnover intentions of employees. It is composed of 6 items, and it is the shortened version of the original scale with a 5-point Likert scale. While the total score is produced by summing all items after reversing the negative items (items no. 2 and 6). A total score of below 18 indicates the employees' desire to stay, but a score above 18 indicates a desire to leave the organization. Lastly, the scale has a Cronbach alpha

coefficient of 0.91, which translates to a high and acceptable reliability rating.

D. Data Gathering Procedure

The data collection period was from October 22 to November 23, 2021. The researcher used google forms to create an online version of the survey questionnaire and distributed the link via institutional emails and private messages. The responses were only accepted from respondents who completed the form and met the criteria of being a teaching or non-teaching employee of Dr. Carlos S. Lanting College. Finally, after obtaining the required number of participants, the collected responses were tabulated and analyzed using statistical methods.

E. Statistical Treatment

The collected data from the google forms were extracted into an excel spreadsheet, and data were analyzed using the IBM - Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS). At the same time, the statistical treatment of descriptive analysis was used to analyze the frequency and percentage of the demographics profile. Next, the Pearson correlation coefficient was used to determine the relationship of the quality of work life factors and turnover intentions, and lastly, the multiple regression analysis was used to determine the significant prediction between the quality of work life factors (development, participation, compensation, supervision, and work environment) and turnover intentions of teaching and non-teaching employees at Dr. Carlos S. Lanting College.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	1	2	3	4	5
Quality of Work Life Factors	1. Development	3.85	0.97	-			
	2. Participation	3.87	0.97	0.75*	-		
	3. Compensation	3.78	0.88	0.58*	0.65*	-	
	4. Supervision	4.02	1.07	0.62*	0.72*	0.68*	-
	5. Working Environment	3.96	0.95	0.76*	0.79*	0.76*	0.81*
6. Turnover Intentions	14.67	4.40	-0.04	-0.10	-0.29*	-0.15**	-0.26*

Table 2: Correlation Analysis of Variables

p* < .01 (two-tailed), *p* < .05 (one-tailed)

Table 2 presented that employees have moderate levels of quality of work life which are the factors of development (*M* = 3.85; *SD* = 0.97), participation (*M* = 3.87; *SD* = 0.97), compensation (*M* = 3.78; *SD* = 0.88), supervision (*M* = 4.02; *SD* = 1.07), and working environment (*M* = 3.96; *SD* = 0.95). However, supervision has the highest mean score, which indicates that employees are highly satisfied with the social support given by their supervisors and/or immediate heads. On the other hand, turnover intentions (*M* = 14.67; *SD* = 4.40) have a mean score of less than eighteen, and therefore as stated by Roodt (2004), the data shows that employees are more likely to stay within the institution.

In addition, the quality of work life factors which are the development, participation, compensation, supervision, and working environment, significantly correlate with each other, and their relationship is deemed as high and strong based on their correlation coefficients. Consequently, turnover intentions has a negative correlation with compensation (*r* = -0.29, *p* < .01), supervision (*r* = -0.15; *p* < .05), and working environment (*r* = -0.26; *p* < .01). The

inverse relationship on compensation and turnover intentions revealed that employees receiving low compensation, whether directly such as their salaries or indirectly such as their benefits, would tend to have higher turnover intentions that later on would lead to leaving the organization. Similarly, little to no felt supervision from supervisors and immediate heads by the employees would result in employees having higher intentions to leave the company. Furthermore, the negative relationship between the working environment and turnover intentions signifies that if an employee feels that the environment is not conducive and safe enough for them to work, then they have higher turnover intention thoughts. It is also the same for the opposite and/or vice versa scenario for the inverse relationship of turnover intentions with compensation, supervision, and working environment. Lastly, the factors development and participation have no significant correlation with turnover intentions; therefore, it means that there is no relationship between the variables.

	<i>B</i>	σ	β	<i>t</i>	
Quality of Work Life Factors	Development	1.39	0.57	0.30	2.44*
	Participation	0.80	0.62	0.17	1.28
	Compensation	-1.28	0.59	-0.25	-2.17**
	Supervision	0.78	0.55	0.19	1.41
	Working Environment	-2.76	0.83	-0.59	-3.31*

Table 3: Multiple Regression Analysis of Variables

*R*² = 0.17; *F* = 6.01*

p* < .01 (two-tailed), *p* < .05 (one-tailed)

The independent variable in this study is the quality of work life with five levels: development, participation, compensation, supervision, and working environment, whereas the dependent variable is the turnover intentions.

In table 3, the result indicates that the regression model between quality of work life and turnover intentions is significant (*R*² = 0.17; *F* = 6.01; *p* < .01). Therefore, this means that quality of work life is really an indicator to measure an employee's turnover intentions and that quality of work life significantly predicts 17% of turnover intentions of employees. Accordingly, Almalki et al. (2012) discovered that employees who are dissatisfied with their

quality of work life had a greater inclination to leave. Earlier research indicates that companies that provide a higher quality of work life are more likely to gain leverage in acquiring and retaining a valuable workforce, and as a result, employees develop a sense of attachment to their organization when their prior expectations are fulfilled (Tarmizi, 2008).

On the other hand, not all factors of quality of work life were significant predictors of employee turnover intentions; in fact, only three factors (H1, H3, and H5) were significant. Results found that development (β = 0.30; *t* = 2.44; *p* < .01) significantly predicts turnover intentions,

therefore, rejecting the hypothesis 1, it shows that development is a positive predictor of turnover intentions. This would mean that when employees receive more training and education, then their turnover intentions would be higher. Similarly, based on the unstandardized regression coefficient value ($B = 1.39$), each percent increase in development results in a 1.39 increase in turnover intention. This is because training raises an employee's value within the organization, and Alkahtani (2015) discovered that trained people leave their organization in search of higher income to apply their new talents, thus increasing their likelihood of being hired by competitors. Similarly, because they have increased their training and knowledge, they have a greater sense of self-worth and confidence, therefore believing that they deserve better working conditions (Bhatt and Sharma, 2019).

Furthermore, it shows that compensation ($\beta = -0.25$; $t = -2.17$; $p < .05$) inversely predicts turnover intentions and supporting the hypothesis 3. It is demonstrated that when employees are dissatisfied with their earned compensation, whether financial or non-financial, then they would be more likely to have higher turnover intentions. Likewise, according to the unstandardized regression coefficient value ($B = -1.28$), one percent increase in compensation results in a -1.28 percent decrease in turnover intention. This is consistent with other research findings that employees should be satisfied with their overall compensation because their attitudes and behaviors are influenced by it (Hassan, 2014). In addition, Dessler's (1997) compensation theory asserts that financial compensation comprises salary, incentives, commissions, and bonuses, whereas non-financial compensation includes health insurance, paid time off, gift cards, awards, and all that is given not in monetary form. However, Higginbotham (1997) showed that pay does not have to be high; rather, it should be fair and competitive in order to retain individuals as they need it to maintain their lifestyle. Additionally, compensation gives a measurable indicator of an individual's value to the organization (Vizano et al., 2021).

Finally, from the results it was found that working environment ($\beta = -0.59$; $t = -3.31$; $p < .01$) has a negative significant effect on turnover intentions and supporting hypothesis 6. This implies that when an employee believes the organizational climate at work is not conducive and safe, they have a greater likelihood of considering leaving the organization. Moreover, based on the data, the working environment had the highest negative unstandardized regression coefficient value ($B = -2.76$), which suggests that a one percent increase in the working environment would lead to a -2.76 percent decrease in turnover intention. Research evidence shows that Ahmad (2013) and Adikoeswanto et al. (2020) found that if a company is able to exert efforts in providing good work and a peaceful environment, it will lead to a comfortable work life which will likely increase an employees' commitment and lessen their intentions to leave. As the work environment is the location where employees perform their daily tasks, a suitable work environment enables employees to work more efficiently. Moreover, given the outbreak of coronavirus disease (COVID-19), employees would prefer to stay in a

safe working environment, protecting themselves from the virus (Wong et al., 2020). Similarly, determining and establishing a positive work environment will determine the organization's success in attaining its goals (Meirina et al., 2018).

V. CONCLUSION

Employees are widely regarded as an organization's most significant asset and the backbone of its success. Thus, an educational institution such as Dr. Carlos S. Lanting College needs to maintain its employees and reduce turnover in order to provide quality services to its clients and learners. In this regard, turnover intentions would be utilized as an operational measure of turnover since this likely predicts the actual behavior, and quality of work life factors are the proposed variables that could alleviate it.

The purpose of this research is to investigate whether the quality of work life factors, specifically development, participation, compensation, supervision, and work environment has an impact on turnover intentions. It is hypothesized that there is an inverse impact of quality of work life factors (development, participation, compensation, supervision, and work environment) on turnover intentions of employees at Dr. Carlos S. Lanting College.

The Pearson correlation analysis indicates that the quality of work life factors significantly correlate with each other, and their relationship is regarded as high and strong based on their correlation coefficients. However, turnover intentions only have a negative correlation with the factors of compensation, supervision, and working environment. On the other hand, the multiple regression analysis showed that overall quality of work life significantly predicts turnover intentions of employees. However, only two hypotheses (H3 and H5) had been supported, which are the compensation and working environment factors that have a negative impact on turnover intentions of employees at Dr. Carlos S. Lanting College. While Chatman's (1989) person-organization fit theory was validated since it asserts that employees will likely remain in an organization if their needs are addressed, in this instance, employees at the institution will likely stay if their compensation and working environment demands are met.

In conclusion, if employees' compensation, whether financial or non-financial, increases and becomes more competitive in comparison to other institutions, and if their working environment is regarded to be conducive, safe, and non-toxic, therefore, turnover intentions of employees are likely to decrease. Hence, the management should place a greater emphasis on compensation and work environment factors in order to manage and reduce employee turnover rate.

Implications from this research provided the management and the human resource department with information to focus on relevant factors that could reduce the turnover rate of employees in the institution. Consequently, given the awareness of the employees' needs through this research, the management should still

implement helpful policies and programs as this will not only be beneficial to the employees but also to the institution over time. Finally, the scope of the study focused on the employees of Dr. Carlos S. Lanting College; therefore, findings from this research could only indicate their perspective and might not be applicable to other companies.

VI. RECOMMENDATION

Based on the research, it is necessary for the institution to treat their employees with utmost concern and attention for their needs, particularly in the aspects of compensation and work environment, to lessen their turnover intentions. Therefore, it is recommended that the management and human resource department should consider having a regular assessment of employees' perception of their working conditions as this could foster and promote greater employee satisfaction and reduce turnover intention. Similarly, the management must compensate the employees adequately and needs to seriously work on creating a compensation scheme. In this regard, the institution should have clear a legislation related to pay packages and promotion policy of teaching and non-teaching employees according to their academic qualification, performance, and experience. Increasing compensation to reduce turnover intentions could be in the form of an increased salary, bonuses, fringe benefits, health insurance, and other benefits. Moreover, additional incentives and recognition may be offered to employees who have served the company for a long period of time and have performed excellently.

Furthermore, it is essential for the management to create a conducive work environment as this serves as a means of enhancing an employee's physical and psychological well-being. This could be achieved by encouraging a healthy, safe, and harmonious work environment for all employees, whether they work on-site at the school or remotely, and by implementing a comprehensive work policy specifically for the pandemic. To be more specific, management should encourage employees to be completely vaccinated and to adhere to health and safety protocols on a regular basis to minimize the risk of contracting the disease. Also, open communication with colleagues and immediate heads, as well as firms that respect employees' work-life balance, can contribute to a positive work environment. In addition, the organization should design further strategies to improve the above recommendations so that the performance and efficiency of employees could be improved, which can reduce turnover intentions ultimately. Likewise, the management should instigate further programs to understand why employees leave the institution and identify issues that attract and retain them in the institution.

It is also recommended that future researchers could replicate the study to complement and validate its findings. Future research could examine more variables and factors of quality of work life as the current study only measured five factors. In order to improve reliability, it is suggested that future research could either broaden or narrow specific industries as different sectors may have distinctly different

employment conditions that could influence employees' outlook. Likewise, it is recommended to further analyze the profile of the workforce such as their sex, age, education, tenure, category, and nature and its effect on the employees' turnover decision in order to widen the scope of understanding and shed more light in the field of the human resource. In-depth research can also further investigate how to solve the turnover intention problem of companies based on the factors, as this could make the study more precise and informative. Finally, qualitative research design with the utilization of interviews with employees can be added into future studies as when both qualitative and quantitative research design is involved in the study, it can improve and enhance the results.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The researchers would like to extend their humble gratitude to Dr. Carlos S. Lanting College for financially supporting this study. Additionally, to the President and CEO, Dr. Dennis Mayer A. Tan, the Senior Vice President, Dr. Nora Velma Gayod, and the Top Management for allowing and giving the researchers an opportunity to conduct this study. Finally, the researchers would like to appreciate the assistance and guidance of the Center for Research and Development, as well as to the Dr. Carlos S. Lanting College Community for their participation in this study.

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APPENDICES

APPENDIX A

Permit to Study Letter

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October 15, 2021

ISO 9001:2015 Certified

DR. DENNIS MAYER A. TAN
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MERVIC M. MANDAP
NUQUIE P. GADIN, RPh,
CHRA
BEA TERESA S. SENGCO,
RPh, CHRA
LOUIE CAMILLE V. DOMINGO

DR. DENNIS MAYER A. TAN
President/CEO

DR. NORA VELMA M. GAYOD
Senior Vice President
Dr. Carlos S. Lanting College

Good day!

We, the researchers from Dr. Carlos S. Lanting College - Human Resources Management Department would like to humbly ask for your consent to permit us to conduct our research entitled "**Working to Leave or Living to Work? A Study on DCLC Employees' Quality Work Life Factors and Its Impact on Turnover Intentions**".

This research aims to investigate the impact of quality of work life factors (i.e. employee development, participation, compensation, supervision, and work environment) on the turnover intentions of the employees of Dr. Carlos S. Lanting College (DCLC). The purpose of the participation of the respondents in this research is to help the researchers answer their investigation by answering the survey questionnaires which will be provided by the researchers once they have given their consent to participate in this study.

Thank you very much.

Respectfully Yours,

The Researchers

has
MS. BEA TERESA S. SENGCO
Co-Author

Gelin
MS. NUQUIE P. GADIN
Co-Author

LC
MR. LEONILO M. CRUZ
Main Author

Noted:
E. Icalia
DR. EVA P. ICALIA
VP for Administration

Service, Excellence, Nationalism

APPENDIX B

Emailed Consent to Use Instruments to Authors

[REQUEST FOR RESEARCH INSTRUMENT] Quality of Work Life's Factors and Their Impacts on Organizational Commitments 🖨️ 📄

Sengco, Bea Teresa <beasengco@lanting.ph.education>
to DodotAdikoewanto_9917919007, anis.eliyana, hamidah, tuty.wulan, agungdharmawan, fadilla740

Tue, Oct 12, 2:08 AM (3 days ago) ☆ ↶ ⋮

Greetings of peace and gratitude!

A pleasure of mine to email the research authors for the journal article entitled "Quality of Work Life's Factors and Their Impacts on Organizational Commitments". I have read your research article and my research team at Dr. Carlos S. Lanting College from the Philippines were highly interested to align our research study to yours specifically in the area of Quality of Work Life Factors of our employees. In connection with this, we are humbly asking for your kind permission of approval as we would like to request your research instruments/questionnaires and their corresponding validity evidence report for us to adapt it in line with the nature of our location and respondents.

Thank you and we are hoping for your positive response.

Bea Teresa Sengco, Rpm, CHRA
Human Resource Staff, Psychometrician,
SHS Teacher, and Researcher
Dr. Carlos S. Lanting College

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TUNROVER INTENTION SCALE CONSENT FORM External Inbox x 🔍 🖨️ 📄

Sengco, Bea Teresa <beasengco@lanting.ph.education>
to groodt

Thu, Oct 14, 9:06 AM (1 day ago) ☆ ↶ ⋮

Dear Prof Roodt,

Good day,

We are currently working on our research related to the turnover intentions of our employees at Dr. Carlos S. Lanting College. In connection with this, we would like to humbly ask for your kind permission of approval for us to have a copy and adapt your Turnover Intention Scale and its validity evidence report in our current research study.

Thank you and we are hoping to hear from you soon.

Bea Teresa Sengco, Rpm, CHRA
Human Resource Staff & Psychometrician
Dr. Carlos S. Lanting College

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APPENDIX B**Emailed Consent to Use Instruments to Authors (Response)**

APPENDIX C**Informed Consent Form****Dr. Carlos S. Lanting College****Project/Research Title:**

“Working to Leave or Living to Work? A Study on DCLC Employees’ Quality Work-life Factors and its Impact on Turnover Intention”

Name of Researchers: Mr. Leonilo M. Cruz
Ms. Bea Teresa S. Sengco
Ms. Nuquie P. Gadin

A. Purpose and Background:

This research aims to investigate the impact of quality of work-life factors (i.e., employee development, participation, compensation, supervision, and work environment) on the turnover intentions of the employees of Dr. Carlos S. Lanting College (DCLC). The purpose of your participation in this research is to help the researcher answer their investigation by answering the survey questionnaires which will be provided by the researchers once you have given your consent to participate in this study.

B. Procedure:

If you agree to participate in this research study, the following will occur:

- You will be given an online form divided into three parts:
 - The first part will collect some of your personal information such as sex, age, educational background, tenure of employment, and nature and category of employment.
 - The second part will be the first of two questionnaires/scales which will gather information about the quality of your work-life factors with DCLC through Likert Scale;
 - The last part will be the second questionnaire/scale that aims to ascertain the extent to which you intend to stay at the institution through Likert Scale.
- Answering the two scales may take 10-20 minutes of your time.

C. Risks

You might or might not feel comfortable in answering some of the questions but rest assured that the researches will treat your data with utmost confidentiality.

D. Confidentiality

The data collected and gathered from this study will be kept confidential. No individual identities will be used in any reports or publications resulting from the study. All survey questionnaires shall be stored separately from any names or other direct identification of participants. The folder containing the survey questionnaires shall be protected with a password to prevent unauthorized access. Also, only the researchers will have access to the said folder.

After the study is completed, all answered questionnaires and data of participants shall be kept for educational/research purposes.

E. Benefits of Participation

There will be no direct benefit to you from participating in this research study. However, participating in this study will help the institution to foster a better quality of work-life factors of each employee in DCLC.

By signing this Informed Consent Form, you...

- Confirm that your participation in this research is voluntary and you have the liberty to withdraw from answering the survey questionnaires any time with or without an explanation;
- Understand that you will not receive any payments and/or compensation for participating in this research;
- Understand that your confidentiality as a participant in this study will remain secure;
- May review your answers and other data collected before submitting it;
- Have read and understood the purpose, procedures, risks, confidentiality, and benefits of participating in this study; and,
- Agree to the terms indicated above.

APPENDIX D**Quality of Work Life Factors Scale**

This scale aims to recognize the quality of your work-life factors (i.e. Employee Development, Participation, Compensation, Supervision, and Working Environment) with DCLC through assessing how much you agree/disagree to every question corresponding to each work-life factor.

We encourage you to answer every item honestly on whether you strongly disagree, disagree, agree, strongly agree, or neither.

Legends:

5 – Strongly Agree; 4–Agree; 3–Neither; 2–Disagree; 1– StronglyDisagree

EMPLOYEE DEVELOPMENT	5	4	3	2	1
1. There is a good opportunity for me to get an education in order to increase my knowledge and ability to do my job.					
2. There is an assessment activity for me in order to find out how my ability improves.					
3. There is a good opportunity for me to occupy a higher position in the future.					
PARTICIPATION	5	4	3	2	1
4. I can participate to be involved in decision making related to work.					
5. I can participate in contributing ideas and suggestions in carrying out work					
6. The company carries out inputs and suggestions from employees well.					
COMPENSATION	5	4	3	2	1
7. The salary I receive is in accordance with my position.					
8. The benefits I receive are in accordance with the years of service I have.					
9. There is recognition of my work by the company.					
SUPERVISION	5	4	3	2	1
10. My supervisor has clear communication skills.					
11. My supervisor has a good ability to make decisions objectively.					
12. My supervisor has a good ability to evaluate the work that has been done.					
WORKING ENVIRONMENT	5	4	3	2	1
13. I feel my company provides security guarantees at work.					
14. I feel that the physical condition of the environment in which I work is good and adequate.					
15. I feel that my working hours are in accordance with the rules.					

APPENDIX E**Turnover Intentions Scale (TIS-6)**

The following section aims to ascertain the extent to which you intend to stay at DCLC. Please read each question and indicate your response using the scale provided for each question by shading/encircling it.

During the past 9 months....

		5	4	3	2	1	
1. How often have you considered leaving your job?	Never						Always
2. How satisfying is your job in fulfilling your personal needs?	Very Satisfying						Totally Dissatisfying
3. How often are you frustrated when not given the opportunity at work to achieve your personal work-related goals?	Never						Always
4. How often do you dream about getting another job that will better suit your personal needs?	Never						Always
5. How likely are you to accept another job at the same compensation level should it be offered to you?	Highly Unlikely						Highly Likely
6. How often do you look forward to another day at work?	Always						Never

AUTHORS' INFORMATION FORM**Title page information for first page of the manuscript****Leonilo M. Cruz**

Dr. Carlos S. Lanting College, Philippines

Bea Teresa S. Sengco

Dr. Carlos S. Lanting College, Philippines

Nuquie P. Gadin

Dr. Carlos S. Lanting College, Philippines

Corresponding Author – CA

Bea Teresa S. Sengco

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Authors Biography

Mr. Leonilo M. Cruz received his Bachelor of Science in Nursing from Dr. Carlos S. Lanting College in 1992 and his Master of Arts in Nursing Administration and Supervision Major in Clinical Instruction from Manila Central University in 1997. He is also a Registered Nurse, and currently working at Dr. Carlos S. Lanting College as the Head of the Human Resource Management Department, Head of the Property Management and General Services Department, Chief Administrative Officer, Internal Auditor, and Assistant Dean of the College of Nursing.

Ms. Bea Teresa S. Sengco received her Bachelor of Arts Major in Psychology from De La Salle Araneta University in 2018 and pursued her Diploma in Industrial Relations from the University of the Philippines Diliman in 2021. She is also a Registered Psychometrician and ranked 8th as a Certified Human Resource Associate. Lastly, she is currently working at Dr. Carlos S. Lanting College as the Human Resource Staff and Psychometrician.

Ms. Nuquie P. Gadin received her Bachelor of Science in Psychology in 2019 and pursued her Master of Arts in Education Major in Administration and Supervision in 2021 both from Dr. Carlos S. Lanting College. She is also a Registered Psychometrician and a Certified Human Resource Associate. Lastly, she is currently working at Dr. Carlos S. Lanting College as the Human Resource Staff.